

SUPERHYDROPHOBIC SELF-REGENERATIVE SILICONE RUBBER NANOCOMPOSITES FOR ELECTRICAL OUTDOOR INSULATION

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ABSTRACT

The overall objective of this project is to develop new structural composite materials for high voltage outdoor insulation applications using silicone rubber (PDMS) coated with micro- and nanoparticles. The goal is to obtain hierarchical superhydrophobic surfaces, with antifogging, antifouling and self-cleaning ability. This will minimize surface leakage currents and subsequent surface flash over of the insulator.

In order to achieve both the superhydrophobic and self-cleaning ability, a combination of different surface chemistry of the particles has been investigated. Three different deposition techniques, including spraying of ROD ultrasonicated ZnO suspensions were investigated.

Pure silicone rubber (SYLGARD[®] 184) was coated with hydrophobic and hydrophilic inorganic micro- and nanoparticles (ZnO). The effect of the different factors, such as particle surface chemistry and the deposition method, on the hydrophobicity of the surface has been investigated using static and dynamic contact angle measurements. The objective has been to achieve the highest static contact angle combined with the lowest possible hysteresis. The results showed that the spraying method was more suitable when using PDMS as matrix. The link between superhydrophobicity and the surface structure has been assessed by Scanning Electron Microscopy.

The next step towards a self-regenerative composite material is approached by the incorporation of the optimal functionalised nanoparticles into the bulk material. The dynamic behaviour of silicone rubber presents a challenge for the stability of micro- and nanocomposites. Different mechanical techniques and methods of integration are being investigated for improvement of the homogeneity of the composites. Preliminary studies have been performed evaluating the effect of the curing time of the PDMS on the degree of incorporation of the nanoparticles in the surface and uniformity within the bulk. The behaviour of the nanocomposite and the evolution of the different properties with time and environmental conditions will be studied in the next phase of the project.

1 INTRODUCTION

Superhydrophobic surfaces provide true protection from pollution and material deterioration for a range of electrical applications. The materials are exposed to a variety of environmental degradation factors, e.g. UV, heat, rain and biological attack. The surface structures can be optimized for self-cleaning/hydrophobicity thereby easily removing the decomposition products during rain and fog. The recovery factor, present in natural processes, is of high importance. Design of materials with high hydrophobicity and self-cleaning properties can reduce the failures of electrical applications induced by pollution and weather changes. It is therefore important to investigate how these surfaces can be optimized and how they influence the performance of the insulation materials.

World leading suppliers of electro technical equipment are constantly seeking for new designs, using new materials and new phenomena, to keep up with the growing global interest for reliable and sustainable products and systems. The higher performance, reduced weight and the possibilities for completely novel design concepts make use of new polymeric materials very attractive.

Thus, one of the areas with increasing interest in industry and research is how to develop multifunctional structured polymeric composite materials for outdoor insulation with antifouling and antifogging function. The present work focuses on the first part of the mentioned approach, which is the design and characterization of the superhydrophobic and self/cleaning surfaces using silicone rubber as the bulk material and nanoparticles as fillers and nano- and micro-structural elements. The structured surfaces and the bulk of the material provide separate regenerative protection for the different applications [1-3]. Furthermore, the structured composite outdoor insulation materials, which can be used in heavily polluted areas, contribute to reduced leakage currents [4], improving the long-term reliability.

It is important to establish a clear definition of superhydrophobic surfaces as those with both a static contact angle (CA) greater than 150° and a contact angle hysteresis less than 10° [5]. Complementary definitions imply that the sliding/rolling off angle of a water drop deposited on a superhydrophobic surface should also be less than 10° [6].

Hierarchical structured surfaces like the ones exhibited by the Lotus plant leaves naturally accomplish the requirements to be considered as superhydrophobic and have been an inspiration for the design and development of the micro- and nanostructured self-cleaning artificial surfaces [7].

However, it is also common to find nanostructured surfaces with static contact angles above 150° but with contact angle hysteresis (CAH) above 10° , also representing the naturally occurring phenomena called Rose Petal effect. On these surfaces, the water drops don't slide easily and get pinned, and the surfaces are not considered as self-cleaning, which is the target of this work.

Many factors affect the way that water drops behave on a nano-structured surface. In this work, ZnO nanoparticles have been used in order to increase the roughness of silicone rubber surfaces, following the Wenzel and Cassie-Baxter principles, which, in general terms, relate the increase of surface roughness with an increase in the contact angle of a water drop on a hydrophobic surface [8-9]. Furthermore, ZnO has been already tested as an antimicrobial agent, which could provide the surfaces with antifouling properties.

One of the factors that can modify the roughness of the surface is the technique used in order to incorporate or deposit the nanoparticles onto the surfaces. The tendency of the nanoparticles to agglomerate is both an advantage and an inconvenience, since certain agglomeration promotes the micro-size scale, but too high cluster sizes will diminish the effect of the nano-scale effect. Thus, the methods for deposition of nanoparticles should find a balance between both behaviors in order to optimize the roughness. In this work, the ZnO nanoparticles were suspended in a solvent and deposited on the surfaces using three different techniques: spray, dip-coating and pipetting. The potential of the spray technique for hydrophobic coatings using nanoparticles is being studied due to possibility to cover a big range of areas [10]. Since not only the deposition influences the distribution of the particles, two different solvent-evaporating positions were also tested.

Furthermore, the hydrophilicity or hydrophobicity of the nanoparticles is an important factor competing with the roughness effect, since the combination of the roughness and the chemistry of ZnO, in this case, can balance the result from a rose petal performance to a self-cleaning behavior

(Lotus effect). Therefore, the effect of two types of commercial ZnO nanoparticles has been studied, with and without a hydrophobic organo-silane coating.

The combination of all these factors with the dynamic behavior of the PDMS, present a challenge regarding the optimization of a chosen combination of nanoparticles and deposition methods. The continuous diffusion of oligomers from the bulk to the surface in PDMS, allowing the rubber to recover the hydrophobicity, also needs to be addressed regarding the possible loss of roughness achieved by a determined type of deposition.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

Two different types of ZnO nanoparticles were used: Zinc Oxide NanoTek[®] C2 (99%, organo-silane coated, 40-100nm APS Powder, BET=10-25 m²/g) and Zinc Oxide NanoTek[®] (54nm APS Powder, BET=17 m²/g) both purchased from Nanophase Technologies. The coating suspensions were prepared using Ethanol 96% obtained from VWR International. Two different materials were used as substrates: float soda-lime glass slides supplied from VWR International (76x26x1mm) and the polydimethyl siloxane (PDMS) elastomer Sylgard 184[®] (Dow Corning), which consists of a base and a cross linker agent. Isopropyl alcohol \geq 99.7% (SAFC) was used to clean the substrates prior to the coating solution depositions. In order to study the morphology of the surfaces, microscope glass cover slides were used so they could be analysed with a scanning electron microscope.

2.2 Preparation of substrate samples

Two different substrate samples were prepared: The soda-lime glass slides were rinsed with Isopropyl alcohol 10 minutes before to the experiments, and let dry at room temperature in a clean environment in order to avoid any dust deposition prior to the coating process.

The Sylgard 184[®] substrates were prepared mixing the base and the curing agent with a ratio 10:1 respectively as it is indicated by the provider. The mixture was stirred vigorously during 1 minute and then poured into Teflon molds with dimension of 70x20x1 mm. The molds containing the silicone mixture were degassed in a vacuum desiccator during 30 min in order to eliminate the bubbles formed during the stirring and transferring to the molds. Thereafter, the samples were cured at room temperature during 48 hours, according to the curing time-temperature relation given by the provider. The Sylgard 184[®] plates were extracted from the molds, rinsed with Isopropyl alcohol 10 minutes before the experiments and dried at room temperature in a dust-free environment.

The glass substrates and PDMS substrates were kept separated during the whole experimental and analysis process in order to avoid the glass surfaces (both before and after coating) to be contaminated with light weight oligomers from the PDMS substrates. All the PDMS slides were positioned horizontally on clean glass slides, with the surface that faced the air while curing upwards.

2.3 Preparation of the Coating Suspensions

Two different suspensions were prepared with the same concentration: 35 mg/mL of ZnO NanoTek[®] and 35 mg/mL of ZnO NanoTek[®] C2, both in Ethanol 96%. The nanoparticles were mixed with 30 mL of Ethanol 96% and the resultant solutions were ultrasonicated during 5 minutes with a Sonics Vibra Cell ROD Ultrasonicator (450 A, 20kHz at 30% amplitude). Sonication times less than 5 minutes resulted in unstable suspensions of the organo-silane coated nanoparticles. Ethanol 96% was used for both types of nanoparticles suspensions since both types are polar and ethanol has a medium polar molecule with a lower boiling point than water. Both characteristics make Ethanol compatible enough to prepare stable and homogeneous suspensions, and the solvent evaporates fast enough after the deposition to reduce the nanoparticles agglomeration once they are on the substrate surface.

2.4 Deposition of the Coating Suspensions

After the ROD ultra-sonication, each solution was deposited both on the glass and the PDMS substrates following three different deposition techniques explained as follows:

- Spray Deposition: 2 mL of the coating suspension were sprayed using an air brush with a nozzle diameter of 0.3 mm connected to a compressed nitrogen source (1.5 bar). All the substrates were horizontally positioned and sprayed perpendicularly at a constant distance of 130 mm.

- Dip-Coating: The substrates were vertically immersed in the coating suspension and immediately pulled up at a constant speed of 10 cm/s.

- Droplet Pipetting: Three droplets with a volume of 40 μL were deposited at three different positions for every substrate.

Sprayed and dip-coated samples dried in two different positions, horizontal and vertical. Pipetted substrates were only positioned horizontally. The solvent was evaporated at room temperature during 12 hours prior to the characterization, allowing the surfaces to reach a stationary state regarding the oligomers surface covering.

Two blank samples were also prepared for comparison. The samples consisted of glass and PDMS substrates cleaned with Isopropyl alcohol 10 minutes before the characterization. The nomenclature used for the different substrates, ZnO nanoparticles, deposition, drying techniques and blanks is listed in the table below (Table 1).

		Deposition Technique				
		Spray		Dip-coating		Pipetting
Nanoparticles	Substrate	Vertical Drying	Horizontal Drying	Vertical Drying	Horizontal Drying	Horizontal Drying
NanoTek [®]	Glass	G-NT-SV	G-NT-SH	G-NT-DV	G-NT-DH	G-NT-P
NanoTek [®] C2	Glass	G-NTC2-SV	G-NTC2-SH	G-NTC2-DV	G-NTC2-DH	G-NTC2-P
NanoTek [®]	PDMS	P-NT-SV	P-NT-SH	P-NT-DV	P-NT-DH	P-NT-P
NanoTek [®] C2	PDMS	P-NTC2-SV	P-NTC2-SH	P-NTC2-DV	P-NTC2-DH	P-NTC2-P
Blank	Glass	G-Blank				
Blank	PDMS	P-Blank				

Table 1: Nomenclature for the different samples

3 CHARACTERIZATION OF SAMPLES

3.1 Contact Angle Measurements (CAM)

For the characterization of the wetting behavior of the surfaces, static and dynamic contact angle measurements were performed using a CAM200 contact angle meter (KSV Instruments, Helsinki, Finland) with an automatic dispenser.

Regarding the static contact angle measurements, a 4 μL MilliQ deionized water droplet was deposited on the sample for every experiment, and 20 pictures were taken with the CCD camera at 1 frame per second. The images were then analyzed using the instrument software and the Young-Laplace method was selected as the method for the numeric data analysis. The same experiment was performed in at least four different points of the sample and the average value was then considered as the static contact angle of the studied surface.

The average advancing and receding contact angles were also calculated for four different points of the same surface. For every dynamic CAM experiment, a 3 μL droplet was initially positioned on the surface. The volume of the droplet was then increased till 25 μL using a stainless steel needle with an external diameter of 0.4mm, which was centered into the drop. The volume was then continuously increased by injecting water into the drop, and after reaching a volume of 40 μL , the volume was then continuously decreased by withdrawing the liquid till 10 μL . The injection and withdrawal processes were recorded by the CCD camera and the Young-Laplace method was selected for evaluation. The advancing and receding contact angles were determined as the contact angles during the injection and withdrawal processes respectively. The contact angle hysteresis for each surface was calculated as the difference between the advancing and receding angle obtained from these experiments.

3.2 Roll-off angles

In order to complement the characterization of the self-cleaning ability of the surfaces, the roll-off angle for the samples was determined using a controlled tilting platform attached to the CAM200 contact angle meter (KSV Instruments, Helsinki, Finland). The samples were positioned on the platform, which is initially in horizontal position. A 15 μL water droplet was deposited on the surface and the platform was tilted continuously at a rate of 0.1°/s, the CCD camera recorded the images at a determined rate of frames per second. The roll-off angle is defined as the tilting angle of the platform when the droplet starts to move down. The same experiment was performed at four different spots of the same sample, and the roll-off angle was calculated as the average value.

3.3 Field emission scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM)

In order to study the different morphologies of the surfaces depending on the deposition method, substrate type and nanoparticles used, a field scanning electron microscope (FE-SEM) was used (Hitachi S-4800, Tokyo, Japan). In order to improve the resolution and quality of the images at high magnification (20000), the samples were coated with a 4 nm layer of Pt/Pd using an Agar Resolution Sputter Coater (Cressington 208 HR, Cressington Scientific Instruments Ltd. Watford, UK). No coating was needed when the applied magnification was 8000.

The samples were prepared in two different batches regarding the substrate type: small PDMS samples or thin microscope glass cover slips. For every type of method, substrate and nanoparticle, three samples were prepared, mounted on the metal studs and kept in a desiccator at least 48 h prior to the SEM analysis.

3.4 Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM)

In order to perform the topography characterization of the different surfaces, atomic force microscopy (AFM) has been used. The instrument, a Multimode 8 SPM with a Nanoscope control unit (Bruker AXS, Santa Barbara, USA) has been used in the ScanAsyst imaging mode.

4 RESULTS

4.1 Static Contact Angle Measurements (CAM)

The results from the experiments regarding the static contact angles are presented in Table 2. Notice that the experiments related to the nanoparticles ZnO NanoTek[®] C2 are missing since they are still under analysis, as well as the Spray-Vertical-Drying experiments for both types of ZnO nanoparticles.

		Deposition Technique				
		Spray		Dip-coating		Pipetting
Nanoparticles	Substrate	Vertical Drying	Horizontal Drying	Vertical Drying	Horizontal Drying	Horizontal Drying
NanoTek [®]	Glass	----	23,65±5,75	48,79±3,13	25,57±2,27	15,28±1,52
NanoTek [®]	PDMS	----	155,86±1,32	148,06±4,46	140,75±1,65	146,24±5,73
Blank	Glass	38,93±0,9				
Blank	PDMS	108,16±1,38				

Table 2. Static Contact Angle results (deg) on Glass and PDMS substrates with deposited ZnO NanoTek[®] and ZnO NanoTek[®] C2 according to 5 different deposition methods.

The errors in the table represent the standard deviation for every result.

Some illustrative images were taken using the CAM200 CCD camera in order to visualize and compare the differences in the drop shapes and contact angles calculated by the CAM200 software. In Figure 1 the pictures corresponding to the surfaces with ZnO NanoTek[®] deposited on glass substrates are shown. Figure 2 represents the pictures of the static water drops on the PDMS surfaces, also with

hydrophilic ZnO NanoTek[®]. Fig.1a) and Fig.2a) are the images corresponding to the blanks, that is, clean and stable flat glass and PDMS surfaces respectively.

Figure 1: CCD camera images for MilliQ water drops for the samples a) G-Blank, b) G-NT-SH, c) G-NT-DV, d) G-NT-DH and e) G-NT-P

Figure 2: CCD camera images for MilliQ water drops for the samples a) P-Blank, b) P-NT-SH, c) P-NT-DV, d) P-NT-DH and e) P-NT-P

4.2 Advancing and Receding Contact Angles. Contact Angle Hysteresis (CAH)

Advancing and receding contact angles were calculated as the mean values for every type of sample and the contact angle hysteresis (CAH) was obtained as the difference between the advancing (θ_a) and the receding (θ_r) contact angle values for every sample. The error values correspond to the standard deviation.

Only the results corresponding to the samples P-Blank and P-NT-SH are presented in Table 3 since the analysis of the results obtained for the rest of the samples are still under evaluation.

	Deposition Technique		
	Spray Horizontal Drying		
	θ_a	θ_r	CAH
ZnO NanoTek [®] PDMS	168,16±2,37	80,36±9,87	87,80
Blank PDMS	120	70	50

Table 3: Advancing and Receding Contact Angles (deg), and Contact Angle Hysteresis in P-blank and P-NT-SH samples.

The stable θ_a and θ_r were calculated with the assistance of the representation of both advancing and receding contact angle evolution with the baseline length, which is directly related to the volume of the drop, as it is shown in the Figure 3.

Figure 3: CA (deg) vs. Baseline (mm) for the sample P-NT-SH.

The data included for baseline values over 2.96 mm and 3.18 mm were discarded for the calculation of θ_a and θ_r respectively since they are considered within the transition region. The θ_r was obtained between the baseline values of approximately 3.18 mm and 2.40 mm.

4.3 Field emission scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM)

The scanning electron micrographs obtained for samples produced with the method of deposition by spray with horizontal drying position, both for glass and PDMS substrates, are presented in Figures 4 and 5. The Figures represent micrographs at low magnification (400), medium (8000) or high magnification (20000), the later ones with a 4nm Pt/Pd coating.

Figure 4: Scanning electron micrographs of glass substrate sprayed with ZnO NanoTek[®] and dried horizontally, at magnifications of a) 400, b) 8K and c) 20K.

Figure 5. Scanning electron micrographs of PDMS substrate sprayed and dried horizontally with ZnO NanoTek[®] at magnifications of a) 400, b) & c) 8K and d) & e) 20K.

5 DISCUSSION

5.1 Static Contact Angle Measurements (CAM)

The static contact angle results obtained and presented in Table 2 show a clear effect of the ZnO NanoTek[®] nanoparticles on the static hydrophobicity of the surfaces, both glass and PDMS. At the same time, results also show dependence of both the deposition and drying techniques, which are directly related to the distribution pattern and agglomeration of the particles on the surfaces.

According to the nature of both the nanoparticles and the substrates, and since only ZnO NanoTek[®] is being discussed here, two different systems can be categorized depending on the hydrophilic and hydrophobic character of the substrates (glass and PDMS respectively).

The presence of ZnO nanoparticles on a flat glass surface has a different effect depending on the deposition technique employed, but in all cases there is a clear effect, which can be related either to a change in the roughness or to the hydrophilic chemistry of the ZnO NanoTek[®]. Since the roughness can only be increased after the deposition of ZnO, independently of the technique, according to the Wenzel equation, for a hydrophilic surface like glass, an increase in the roughness should imply a decrease in the contact angle [11].

This behavior is observed for all the deposition techniques except for the dip-coating with vertical drying position. In particular, both spray and dip-coating methods, when the samples are dried horizontally, present approximately the same decrease in the CA value, that is, around 14°. However, the pipetting method results in a significant decrease of the CA values, around 23.7°, which is related both to a higher roughness and to a higher effect of the hydrophilicity of the ZnO. Both effects are related to a higher concentration of ZnO on the surface caused by the more located deposition technique and the horizontal drying, which doesn't allow the excess of nanoparticles to distribute in a broader area, resulting in a higher degree of agglomeration and promoting multilayers.

On the other hand, only the dip-coating method with vertical evaporation of the solvent has increased the static CA around 9°. This result suggests that the vertical position of the sample while drying allows the nanoparticles to distribute all over the surface in such a way that the amount of air pockets present under the drop are more numerous and evenly distributed, so the wetting behavior is now closer to the Cassie and Baxter state for hydrophobic surfaces.

When analyzing the results for PDMS substrates, all the deposition methods promoted significantly higher static CA on the hydrophobic surface. Significantly important CA value, above 150°, was observed for samples obtained after spraying and drying horizontally. The dip-coating method results differ depending on the drying position, providing the surface with a CA of 148° when the sample dried vertically and 140° when the position was horizontal. The vertical position while drying promotes the nanoparticles to be distributed in a more broaden area providing the surface with a wider size range of nano- and micro-clusters, as it was also observed for the glass substrates.

5.2 Contact Angle Hysteresis (CAH)

The CAH obtained for PDMS surfaces when sprayed with hydrophilic ZnO NanoTek[®] show a rose petal effect tendency which means that the drops get pinned on the surface and they don't slide or roll off even when the tilting angle is high. Nevertheless the CAH for these samples has been clearly reduced by almost 40° compared to the CAH of a clean PDMS surface. The higher difference is

mainly due to the significant increase in the θ_a of the drops from 120° to 168° , and the slight increase in the θ_r from 70° to 80° , for clean PDMS and sprayed PDMS respectively.

The advancing contact angle improvement is related to the observed rise in the static contact angle, since both angles are analyzed when the drop gets in contact with a dry surface. The higher value of the θ_a ($\sim 168^\circ$) compared to the static CA ($\sim 156^\circ$) is due to the presence of resistance forces against the advancing movement of the drop in the 3 phase contact-line.

However, when the surface has already been wetted, the improvement in the θ_r is not as high as the one observed for the θ_a . Since the θ_r itself is decreased to $\sim 80^\circ$ from $\sim 168^\circ$ corresponding to the θ_a , it is understandable that the wetting behavior has changed and the air pockets previously under the drop have been filled with water and the wetting behavior is now closer again to a Wenzel state. This is justified by the hydrophilic character of ZnO nanoparticles, so the hydrophilic character prevails over the roughness effect and the drop gets pinned during the draining process.

4.3 Field emission scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM)

The different morphologies and distribution patterns were observed when comparing the hydrophilic ZnO sprayed and dried horizontally both on hydrophilic and PDMS substrates.

In the low magnification micrograph (8K) the homogeneous distribution of the particles sprayed on the glass hydrophilic surface is clearly seen. This image contrasts with the bigger clusters observed in the PDMS micrographs due to the incompatibility between the hydrophobic matrix and oligomers covering the surface and the hydrophilic particles. During higher magnification analysis of sprayed PDMS substrates it was possible to observe a more heterogeneous surface-height distribution, with some bigger clusters in some areas and less covered areas, providing a more hierarchical structure of the surfaces and resulting in the higher contact angles already observed.

In the highest magnification micrographs it is also possible to detect the softened edges of the ZnO clusters when the substrate is PDMS. This might be due to the oligomers covering the surface, providing a hydrophobic layer to the hierarchical structure, and resulting in higher contact angles.

6 CONCLUSIONS

Different methods for deposition of ZnO nanoparticles suspensions have been used, including pressurized spray, in order to approach hierarchical superhydrophobic self-cleaning surfaces. The study has been performed both on hydrophilic glass surfaces and hydrophobic PDMS Sylgard 184[®], and two different types of ZnO NanoTek[®], with and without organo-silane functionalization.

The deposition pattern of the nanoparticles on the surface was highly influenced by the use of the spray method, resulting in static CA values of a superhydrophobic surface. An important improvement of CAH was observed for PDMS substrates when using the spray deposition technique, but the lotus effect has not been reached with hydrophilic ZnO. Nevertheless, it is expected to obtain a significant decrease in the CAH values when analyzing the results obtained for hydrophobic ZnO NanoTek[®] C2.

SEM images have confirmed the differences in the topography and hierarchy of the sprayed surfaces depending on the substrate nature, and the results have been related to the increased values for the static CA on sprayed PDMS samples.

More analyses of the experiments with ZnO NanoTek[®] C2 are being carried out and are planned to be presented during the conference.

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